

ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction:

In the modern days all most all the countries are trying to develop themselves. Countries are classified under three heads as follow:

- A) Developed Country
- B) Developing Country
- C) Undeveloped Country

This classification is depend-up on the utilization of natural resources.

The country which is succeeded to use the available resources fully for the production is called developed country. If the process of utilization of resources is going on for the production in the country then that country is called developing country. If the country is having resources but country has no power to use the resources for production that country is known as un-developed country. But now a days no country is undeveloped, therefore countries are classified only under two heads as developed and developing or underdeveloped country. The development of economy is depend-up on the entrepreneurship.

1.2 Entrepreneurship:

- 1) It is a process undertaken by an entrepreneur to augment his business interest. It is an exercise involving innovation and creativity that will go towards establishing his/her enterprise.
- 2) Entrepreneurship is the prosperity of mind to take calculated risks with confidence to achieve a pre-determined business or industrial objectives.
- 3) Entrepreneurship is the purposeful activity of an individual or a groups of associated individual undertaken to initiate maintain or organize a profit oriented business unit for the

production or distribution of economic goals and serves. - A. H. Cole.

Meaning:

The word entrepreneur is associated with business; since land labour capital and entrepreneur are consider as important factors of production, the entrepreneur utilize those factors for business activity. The entrepreneur and labour are human factors where as capital and land are not. Entrepreneur is the person who generally floats the idea of business. In other words he is promoter of business. He collects capitals organize the workers and other necessity of business. It is regarded as attitude towards doing business. He is man on the mission. He has accepted the idea of providing jobs instead of performing jobs. In some cases he is the person who provides capital without taking active part in business. But this can be a traditional view. In modern world along with capital he provides idea, innovation and style of performing business.

Entrepreneurship is the function of entrepreneur. It is process of performing the necessities require to float, maintain and expand the business activity. It is action – goal oriented taste. It involves accepting challenge, skillful management risk taking attitude, innovative ideas and professional decision making. It is processes of doing business in a new and better way. He always thinks bigger and better. It is a function of investing in various production lines for achievement and desire objectives. It involves the activity like rising capital, hiring labour arranging for supply of new material and selection of good human resource, for the day to day operations and enterprise.

1.3 Role of Entrepreneurs:

A) Entrepreneur works as decision maker:

What to produce? Where to produce? & How to produce? This basic decision is taken by the entrepreneur. To increase the production, productivity, to minimize the cost of production, full utilization factors of production, for all these decisions are taken by the producer. These countries of producer take the economy towards the development.

B) Capital Formation:

The entrepreneur can generate capital for business. It is essential factor of the production. Capital generates employment opportunities. the generation of capital is easy task for enterprise having market standing or goodwill.

C) Contribution in the International Trade:

The enterprise can share in country's international trade. This contribution is vital of balance of trade as well as balance of payment. The enterprises can contribute towards Govt. exchanger by way of corporate taxes, and indirect taxes and service tax. The enterprises can provide quality goods and services to people.

D) Innovating Nature:

The entrepreneur tries to use invention in the production which is known as innovation. Due to this productions use made available for consumer in the domestic and world market. This helps to develop both the markets and this also helps to develop the economy.

E) Creation of Employment Opportunities:

The role of Eentra in creating employment is also very important. After 1991 in India the industrial sector creating maximum employment opportunities, Eentras also creating trained officers, accountants, managers, workers through training centres.

F) Providing Services to Country:

The entrepreneurs are providing various marketing and financial services to the country. This help to satisfaction of time and place utility. The services are essential for country's economic development. The trade and commerce is not possible without the commercial consultancy and marketing services.

G) An Increase in National Income:

Through the production of export goods, producers help the nation to achieve foreign currency. Through this way our domestic income also increases.

H) Increase in Standard of Living:

In India the Standard of Leaving of people is increasing due to an increase in income and availability of innovated goods and services for consumption.

I) Increase in Per-Capita Income:

Due to the expansion of production & employment the income of the

people is increasing day-by-day as compared to the back years. This also helps to increase in per capital income.

J) Regional Equal Economic Development:

For overall economic development, regional equal development is must. Entraps create regional development. After 1991 particularly most of the producers started the innovated production in those areas which are backward, barren. So these areas are also developing due to entraps.

1.4 Conclusion:

Entrepreneurs work as heart of the body of economy. They take economy towards development through the expansion of production in all the fields such as agriculture, industry, road trade, communication, education etc. The credit of rapid economic development of India after independence goes to the entrepreneurs.

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